

CERTAINTY MPIMET's DMP

Version 0

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for model output created at the MPI-MET is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

The DMP for model output at MPI-MET is designed to maximize the value, accessibility, and impact of the data produced, supporting the Institute's mission in advancing meteorological research and services.

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CERTAINTY

Researchers

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Organizations

MPI Hamburg - Max-Planck-Institut für Meteorologie

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [CERTAINTY MPIMET's DMP](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for model output created at the MPI-MET is developed in the context of effectively managing and preserving valuable data generated for CERTAINTY project.

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#)||[EC](#)

Grants: [CERTAINTY](#)

Project: [CERTAINTY](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Input data for ICON

In its limited-area setup ICON will use input data from ERA-5 including:

1. Vertical profile of state variables
2. Surface conditions
3. initial conditions

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

ERA5 data will be utilized to initialize and force the model. Data set are made available through DKRZ, where we also run the simulations:

https://docs.dkrz.de/doc/dataservices/finding_and_accessing_data/era_data/index.html

For licence, citation and DOI go to
<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

ERA5 is the fifth generation ECMWF reanalysis for the global climate and weather for the past 8 decades.

Reanalysis uses past observations as input data to model simulations to arrive as best estimates of past global weather. This results in a globally complete and consistent dataset.

1.1.5 What is its format?

GRIB

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1 TB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To develop a product

ERA5 are used as initial and boundary conditions of ICON simulations.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.143582cf>

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://codes.ecmwf.int/grib/param-db/>, conventions:
<http://cfconventions.org>

ERA data is compliant with CF conventions: <http://cfconventions.org>

<https://codes.ecmwf.int/grib/param-db/>

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

ERA5

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Any tool able to access GRIB or NETCDF data

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset / output.

html or account at DKRZ

https://docs.dkrz.de/doc/dataservices/finding_and_accessing_data/era_data/index.html

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset / output.

There is no specific tool needed to access the data. As mentioned above any open source tool capable to access and manipulate netcdf data can be used.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

https://docs.dkrz.de/doc/dataservices/finding_and_accessing_data/era_data/index.html

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

At DKRZ the data can be accessed as long as the associated data project is running. In any case the data can be accessed via the copernicus data store. So far a termination of data access at DKRZ is not envisioned.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

n/a

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

Please refer to <https://codes.ecmwf.int/grib/param-db/>

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

please refer to <https://codes.ecmwf.int/grib/param-db/>

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

Please see <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-complete?tab=doc>

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Other (Attribution)

Copernicus license:

<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Re-use

Data availability and re-usability is assured by DKRZ.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of national infrastructure

Infrastructure resource allocations at DKRZ are free of charge for German-based projects in climate science.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

ERA5 data at DKRZ are maintained by the DKRZ data management department.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

ICON output

Limited area model output to investigate the effects of aerosol and the representation of microphysical processes on cloud evolution in selected test cases.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

Similar data has not been produced. ICON limited area model in combination with a microphysical particle model has not been used before to investigate ACI.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Simulation

Time evolution of three dimensional data of physical cloud properties.

1.1.5 What is its format?

zarr

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

100 TB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

Data will be used to study processes, interpret observations, and constrain aerosol-cloud interactions.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

ICON in a limited area setup driven by ERA5 data: <https://www.icon-model.org/>

Model configurations and run script to obtain the simulations will be saved and made available.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education

Project partners;

Beyond the duration of the project the data may be useful to the broad atmospheric and climate science community.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://www.icon-model.org/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers

Handle

Data will be long-term archived by using DKRZ's DOKU service:
https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/info?site=submitinfo_comparison

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Structural
- Reference

We offer descriptive metadata that enriches data or information resources with detailed information about their content, context, and structure, thereby improving their findability and practical use.

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Other

Basic metadata are searchable via the WDCC interface: <https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/q>

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

The DKRZ DOKU service allows for the specification of fit-for-purpose keywords.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

OAI-PMH

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

DKRZ DOKU

https://www.wdc-climate.de/docs/DOKU_User_Guide.pdf

DOKU offers long-term archiving for Earth System data and climate-related products. It is hosted by the German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ) in Hamburg and is maintained by its Data Management (DM) department.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Uses non-proprietary formats

- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

DOKU storage quota will be applied for in conjunction with the resource allocation request associated with the project.

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOKU at DKRZ provides handles

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Limited area simulations with ICON for selected tropical regions

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

Open without embargo

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

During the active research phase of the project data will be stored on a parallel file system at DKRZ and therefore only be accessible by project partner. Subsequently the data will be made available on DOKU. Once the data are archived in DOKU, the dataset will become publicly available, and accessible to all under the CC BY 4.0 license.

DKRZ tracks the access to specific datasets stored in the longterm archive by its users due to the authentication procedures in place. The reports are used only internally at DKRZ and are not openly accessible and not provided to data providers.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

MPI-MET maintains a policy of retaining modeling data for a period of 10 years. Should external users continue to utilize the data extensively, this retention period may be prolonged.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

Yes. However, we will not have closed datasets

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

Direct links are provided

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

Metadata in DOKU are free text

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

Yes

Mapping to CF conventions will be provided

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

Yes

The dataset will be linked with the related scientific articles and also with the input data.

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

No embargo once the associated publication is published

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

- Readme files
- Variable definitions
- Units of measurement

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

Output data will be openly accessible and associated research will be published in scientific publications.

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

No

Provenance will not be documented using standard approaches but we will provide documentation to ensure the traceability of results.

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

The data quality is as good as the ICON model.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

DKRZ services are free of charge for scientific projects associated with the German climate science community and who have been granted IT resources at DKRZ.

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of national infrastructure

DKRZ is the national IT service provider for the German climate science community.

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

The data will be preserved following DKRZ's DOKU guidelines: https://www.wdc-climate.de/docs/DOKU_User_Guide.pdf

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures

All the minimum conditions listed in Science Europe Guidance Document are covered by the WP6 Open Science and Data management

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